

The non-native *Areca triandra* palm is a potential threat to the Southwestern rainforests of Sri Lanka

Supporting material

Appendix 1: Invasiveness assessment protocol (*Criteria for categorizing invasive nonnative plants that threaten wildlands* by Warner et al 2003) evaluated under three main criteria;

Q.1. invasive potential, Q.2. reproductive potential and Q.3. ecological amplitude.

(A - High, B - Moderate, C - Low, D - Negligible, U - Unknown)

Criteria and Explanation	Result
Q 1. Ecological Impact	
Q 1.1 Impact on abiotic ecosystem processes	
Alteration and impact on the natural range, variation of abiotic ecosystem processes, ability of native species to survive and reproduce.	Moderate alteration of the ecosystem processes (B)
Q 1.2 Impact on plant community composition, structure, and interactions	
Cumulative ecological impact to the plant communities. Reduction in propagule dispersal, seedling recruitment, survivorship of native species, change in horizontal distribution patterns or fragmentation of native community.	Moderate alteration of plant community composition (B)
Q 1.3 Impacts on higher trophic levels	
Impact on all native species, significant reduction in native species' nesting or foraging sites, cover, or other critical resources (native species habitats).	Moderate alteration of populations, communities/ interactions (B)
Q 1.4 Impact on genetic integrity	
Can hybridize with and influence the proportion of individuals with non-native genes within populations of native species.	Unknown (U)
Score: B	
Q 2. Invasive Potential	
Q 2.1 Role of anthropogenic and natural disturbance in establishment	

Species' dependence on disturbance (human and natural) for establishment in wildlands. E.g. altered hydrology due to dams, diversions, irrigation, etc.; roads and trails; constructions, runoff, natural disturbances	Moderate - establish independent of natural/ anthropogenic disturbances (B)
Q 2.2 Local rate of spread with no management	
Spread in existing localized infestations when no management measures are implemented.	Increases, but less rapidly (B)
Q 2.3 Recent trend in total area infested within state	
Overall trend in the total area infested by this species statewide. rapidly	Increasing, but less rapidly (B)
Q 2.4 Innate reproductive potential	
Rate of maturation: Reaches reproductive maturity in 2 years or less (U), Reproduces by seed: Dense infestations produce >1,000 viable seeds per square meter (2), Populations produce seeds every year (1), Seed production sustain over 3 or more months within a population annually (1), Seeds remain viable in the soil for 3 or more years (U), Viable seed produced with both self-pollination and cross-pollination (U), Reproduces vegetatively: Quickly spreading vegetative structures (1), Fragments easily and fragments can become established elsewhere (0), Resprouts readily when cut (1)	Moderate reproductive potential (4 -5 points) (B)
Q 2.5 Potential for human-caused dispersal	
Potential to be spread by direct or indirect human activity, overcome natural barriers to dispersal, Mechanisms for dispersal include commercial sales, ornamental horticulture, or aquariums; used as forage, spread along transportation corridors such as highways, railroads, trails, or canals.	High - There are numerous opportunities for dispersal to new areas (A)
Q 2.6 Potential for natural long-distance dispersal	
Potential to be spread by animals/ abiotic mechanisms to move seeds. Fruit/ seed is commonly consumed by birds/ other animals that travel long distances.	Frequent long-distance dispersal by animals (A)
Q 2.7 Other regions invaded	

Whether this species has invaded ecological types in other states or countries outside its native range.	Invades elsewhere but only in ecological types that it has already invaded (C)
Score: B	
Q 3. Ecological Amplitude and Distribution	
Q 3.1 Ecological amplitude	
The number and proportion of different ecological types invaded, Competitive ability, Forms dense thickets, climbing or smothering growth habits or otherwise.	Moderate - naturalized and invaded in tropical and subtropical regions (B)
Q 3.2 Distribution	
Percentage of the ecological type's total number of occurrences (frequency) that have been invaded. Current global distribution. The known level of impact in natural areas.	Unknown (unable to estimate the percentage of global occurrences invaded) (U)
Score: C	
Overall score: B	
Status: Alert	